

*Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.*

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

DOCUMENT INFORMATION	5
DOCUMENT HISTORY	6
DISCLAIMER	6
DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1. INTRODUCTION	9
2. THE CONCEPT OF « PRACTICE » TO SUPPORT THE DESCRIPTION OF TERRITORIAL ECOSYSTEMS	10
2.1. WHY DESCRIBE ACTORS, THEIR OBJECTIVES, AND THEIR CONTEXT?	11
2.2. WHY DESCRIBES PRACTICES?	13
3. DATA COLLECTION TOOLS	14
4. OUTCOMES	14
5. DATA TREATMENT: DESCRIPTION OF THE TERRITORIAL ECOSYSTEMS FOR DIGITALIZATION ..	21
5.1. WHO IS INVOLVED?	21
5.2. WHO ARE THE BENEFICIARIES?	22
5.3 AN ECOSYSTEM WITH MANY INTERACTIONS	23
5.4 THE TARGETED IMPACT OF THE PRACTICES ON THE DIGITALIZATION MATURITY OF THE BENEFICIARIES	25
5.5 THE MAIN CLAIMED OBSTACLES	29
6. DIGITALIZATION AND RRI IN TERRITORIES	31
7. DESCRIPTION OF THE MAIN PRACTICES FOR DIGITALIZATION	34
7.1 TRAINING	34
7.2 TECHNICAL PLATFORMS.....	36
7.3 CLUSTERING	37
7.4 INTEGRATION OF USERS IN SERVICE DESIGN	38
7.5 POOLING OF SERVICES.....	38
7.6 PROMOTION OF FREE SOFTWARE.....	39
7.7 RESEARCH	39
7.8 STRATEGIC PLAN.....	39
7.9 INVESTMENT FOR OPTICAL FIBRE	39
7.10 SUPPLY OF COMPUTER EQUIPMENT	40
8. CONCLUSION	41
REFERENCES	42
ANNEX	43
DIGITERRI TASK 2.4: DATA COLLECTION GUIDELINES	43

TABLE OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1:	A DIGITAL MATURITY MODEL TO REPRESENT PRESENT SITUATION AND OBJECTIVE OF EACH PRACTICE	12
FIGURE 2:	NUMBER OF PRACTICES DESCRIBED PER COUNTRY	20
FIGURE 3:	BENEFICIARIES PER PRACTICE AND PER TARGETED DOMAIN.	22
FIGURE 4:	TYPES OF CONTRACTS BETWEEN STAKEHOLDERS.	24
FIGURE 5:	FORM AND PECUNIARY DIMENSION OF THE PARTNERSHIPS (DP-N REFERS TO THE DIGITAL PRACTICE NUMBER N).	25
FIGURE 6:	EXPECTED DIGITAL MATURITY LEVEL FOR EACH PRACTICE AND EACH DIMENSION.	26
FIGURE 7:	CURRENT DIGITAL MATURITY DIAGRAM FOR EACH OF THE PRACTICES AND EACH DIMENSION.	28
FIGURE 8:	RRI EVALUATION OF EACH DIGITAL PRACTICE.	31

TABLE OF TABLES

TABLE 1. LIST OF OBSERVED PRACTICES	14
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Description of the deliverable (3-5 lines)	DigiTeRRI includes a phase of territorial diagnosis and in particular a qualitative analysis of the initiatives taken by regional ecosystems in favour of digitization. WP 2.4 has identified voluntary and entrepreneurial practices carried out in Värmland, Styria and Grand Est, whose RRI dimension was then studied.
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DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS

A practice is an organized and formalized action with well-defined means that aims to support the digitization of well-defined beneficiaries with due respect to RRI principles.

Digital maturity model: a representation of the level of proficiency of a structure in a particular domain of digitalization. This model helps in the diagnosis of the studied organization.

RRI: Responsible research and innovation.

DPn: a practice that aims at facilitating the digitalization of some beneficiaries. It is ranked as n in our practices panel.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is a qualitative description of some the practices processed by territorial ecosystems in the field of digitalization. This work complements the already published quantitative diagnostics of the three territories involved in the DigiTeRRI project: Värmland, Styria and Grand Est. It addresses the precise description of certain key actions undertaken in the territories in order to grasp: the entrepreneurial character of each territory, the vision of the actors themselves about the problems to be solved to achieve digitalization, and, their interrelationships.

Data collection has been conducted by the DigiTeRRI project members. They followed a methodology based on past and recent European Union projects about RRI (Responsible Research & Innovation) and additional scientific inputs. This includes a questionnaire, a data collection platform, a video tutorial and a data analysis programming). In total, 36 practices have been studied.

Globally, the study highlights that in each territory the offer of digitalization assistance is “overlapping”. All categories of the population can have access to multiple interlocutors. The context is therefore rich, entrepreneurial and very little categorized. All stakeholders develop partnerships (mainly formal) that build a complex ecosystem: each digital practice entails (in a mean value) 4-5 partnerships. If the level of skill of citizens is a real challenge for this ecosystem, the priority is still on technical dimensions: product innovation, digitization of organizational flows and production management. Moreover, we note that in terms of ambition (meaning “progress expected from the beneficiaries”), the technical areas come first while the expected impact on the governance of structures and leadership is less of a priority. Taking the digital evolution within educational programs is also a major concern. Ten categories of practices have been defined with particular innovative characteristics: teaching, investment in optical fibre, supply of computer equipment, technical platforms, clustering, pooling of services, integration of users in service design, research programs, promotion of freeware, and, territorial strategic plans.

The RRI evaluation of these practices attests that “*gender equality*” is rarely a formalized goal but constitutes a principle followed by stakeholders. “Users integration” is developed widely, moreover, “*Non-corporate*” and “*Value*

diffusion" dimensions of the RRI are taken into account, but less for practices targeting specific social groups. Meanwhile, *communication* is meant to be important and digitized (web). In half of the cases, this communication passes partly through *scientific* channels. The actors largely call upon nearby *public institutions* and *academics* to design and implement their practice. The consultation of *elected politicians* is not a rare phenomenon. Actors seek to place themselves in a context of efficiency by generating *Value* in a significant way and being aware of the few *risks* involved. The *protection of personal data* is generalized.

1. INTRODUCTION

The objective 1 of the DigiTeRRI project consists in characterizing and mapping the three current territorial R&I ecosystems, i.e. those of Värmland in Sweden, Grand Est in France and Styria in Austria. The aim is to draw up a qualitative and quantitative assessment and to put in evidence the characteristics of the three territories involved in DigiTeRRI. These three territories have a history in traditional industry. It was therefore necessary to assess These results provide solid empirical analysis and qualitative and quantitative data for a better understanding of R&I in terms of society, economy, geography, and environment.

This report focuses on the qualitative dimension. It aims to complement the quantitative approach of each territory (see deliverable D2.3 of DigiTeRRI project) with an inventory of "practices" of territorial support to digitalization.

A practice is an organized and formalized action with well-defined means that aims to support the digitization of well-defined beneficiaries with due respect to RRI principles. The aim of Task 2.4 is therefore to understand the initiatives taken by territorial actors in the field of digitization. At this stage of DigiTeRRI the goal is neither to be prescriptive nor to establish recommendations to increase the impact of digitization on a particular area of the RRI as for projects such as RETHINK (scientific communication) and ORION (open science) do. We start from "what's going on in territories" and confront the information to RRI principles. These practices are interesting to know because they translate:

- The entrepreneurial character of each territory: it gives an image of the responsibilities that some actors voluntarily assume,
- The vision of the actors: reflecting their own concern about the problems to be solved to achieve digitalization,
- The interrelationships between actors: it gives a better understanding about the modes of collaboration adopted to federate skills and local energies.

Thus, we can consider that we are interested, as in the TeRRItoria and RRI 2scale projects, in the relationship between a European challenge (digitalization) and initiatives that are local and more precisely territorial.

In addition, this study (work package 2 - task 2.4) is a source of cross-territorial creativity. It involves observing practices and evaluating them based on the RRI principles and then considering their transferability (work package 3). Thus, the study of territorial practices leads to a better understanding of the "dynamic" specificities of the three territories and also serves as a basis for possible cross-fertilization.

The emphasis here is on the operational dimension of digital transformation. The aim is not to be exhaustive, but rather to study a set of specific situations and to find in the diversity of projects carried out in the territories issues that local actors have been able to identify, issues that could have escaped a purely quantitative approach.

2. THE CONCEPT OF « PRACTICE » TO SUPPORT THE DESCRIPTION OF TERRITORIAL ECOSYSTEMS

Today, territories are spaces where actors of various natures have become aware of the stakes of the digital transformation of society. These actors are working to disseminate these issues and offer support for the digital transformation. These aids are varied: awareness-raising, training, technical support, provision of financial resources, advice and support for the reflection of individuals or companies among others. There is therefore a set of practices supported by an R&I ecosystem that can be observed in each territory. Many of these practices have their own specificity due to the local context, the ambitions of the actors, the possibility of setting up partnerships or the culture or the legislative context. The ambition of DigiTeRRI's task 2.4 is to better describe and understand these territorial practices.

To describe the R&I ecosystem we have chosen to:

- a. Describe the actors involved, their objectives and their context,
- b. Describe their practices.

To do so, the theoretical framework is based on

- a. Conceptual elements from: Personas concepts and multi-agent approaches and a Digital Maturity Model,
- b. Conceptual elements from: The Practical/Task/Observable Phenomenon Model (Boly, 2014). This model refers to the theories of evaluation and systemic stating that any process may be described by practices (mobilizing inputs and producing outputs). Then, each practice can be divided into tasks (sequence of activities achieved by people). Finally, the proof that a task has been carried out is provided by a tangible element observable by any evaluator (document, transformed material...).

2.1. Why describe actors, their objectives, and their context?

In each territory, an ecosystem is mobilized to help beneficiaries to digitalize. These R&I ecosystems are complex and characterized by: the multiplicity of actors (schools, universities, public economic institutions, banks, companies, advising companies, clusters, cities and associations), the numerous interrelationships between actors and the specificity of the actions. Therefore, in order to develop a solid protocol for collecting qualitative data to describe these ecosystems, we draw inspiration from various approaches such as personas and the multi-agent theory. This allows us to define descriptive variables of the actors of the territorial ecosystems and to establish data collection forms that are then administered by DigiTeRRI's partners.

Personas are descriptive models of archetypal users. They constitute a generalization of the goals, motivations and behaviours of many individuals (Marshall et al, 2015). This persona principle leads to the definition of the following descriptive variables of a territory's R&I ecosystem: the needs of stakeholder groups, their requirements and goals (Cooper, 1999; Adlin et al., 2006). The personas are fictitious but are based on knowledge of real users. A user-centred qualitative research methodology is needed to ensure that the models created are representative (Gudjonsdottir, 2010). Therefore, we opted for interviews (face-to-face or remote) of some actors in the territories. Without pursuing a modelling goal, we have also been inspired by the principle of multi-agent approaches that insist on the notions of "role" and "own objectives" to define the functioning of a set of actors and their interrelationships (Madjoub et al,2010; Monticolo et al., 2020).

Thus, within the framework of DigiTeRRI's task 2.4, the data collection methods were focused on, not only the identification of the actors of the ecosystem under study, but also of their beneficiaries (individuals and groups wishing to benefit from digitization). These beneficiaries can be citizens, companies, students...

The stakeholders behave according to an expected impact in terms of digitalization in the beneficiary. We have distinguished these expected results according to the 3 levels of digitization:

- Digitation: the actors want to solve a technical problem of digitization,
- Digitization: part of the company's process is to be digitized and is the subject of a project,
- Implementation of digitalization: the actors set up an organization in the company to manage the digitalization (strategy, partnership, new positions ...).

The level aimed at by the beneficiary is, therefore, to be known and reflects the digitization objective aimed at by a given actor. The concept of maturity is then chosen to assess internal processes (Antunes et al., 2014; Wendler, 2012).

In order to further specify the objectives of digitization, we have opted for a Digital Maturity Model (Brumann and Petter, 2019). It is a reference that describes the initial situation and the desired future for the target to be digitized (Andersen et Jessen (2003)).

		Maturity levels				
		Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Dimension	1. Strategy	Strategic vision, transformation roadmap				
	2. Leadership	Management methods, sponsorship, resources				
	3. Products	Business model, innovation capabilities, digital value chain				
	4. Operations	Channels & business practices, processes, agility				
	5. Culture	Customer centricity, hierarchy vs. network, openness				
	6. People	Roles, expertise, capabilities				
	7. Governance	Communication & collaboration rules, KPIs, alignment				
	8. Technology	Software tools, cloud architecture, ICT infrastructure, Industry 4.0				

Source: *Digital transformation report 2014, Eine empirische Studie, Neuland vision&transformation.*

Figure 1: A Digital Maturity Model to represent present situation and objective of each practice

The “dimension” indicates the expected effects of the practice, which is what the change in the beneficiary should be about. It may involve helping the beneficiary to integrate digital technology into its strategic policy, to change its internal management, to train staff or to opt for technical support (logistics, manufacturing process or product). In addition, an increasing “level” is set, ranging from complete ignorance by the beneficiary to his expertise and autonomy. This level describes the present situation and the one that is targeted.

Within the framework of task 2.4, the partners used this Digital Maturity Model to describe each practice.

Finally, the context of the practice must also be considered: it is therefore necessary to know if the beneficiary pays and/or if the ecosystem intervenes within the framework of a collective transversal operation.

2.2. Why describes practices?

A practice is defined as the sum of activities carried out to achieve a result for the recipient by mobilizing resources. Any practice must be objectified by tangible facts, i.e. observable phenomena(s) proving its existence. The observable phenomena thus play the role of indicators allowing the evaluation of the activity in question. If these observable phenomena are present within the company, the activity that they characterize can be considered to be under control. In our case, the mastery of a practice is studied from the perspective of the RRI dimensions: gender equality, science education, open access, public engagement, and ethics.

This approach is complementary to those develop in previous RRI research, that emphasize sociotechnical imaginaries to analyse digital strategies at national level (Wittrock et al., 2021). Moreover, the goal is not to understand the explicit codes of conduct proposed by stakeholders but to discuss the way they are operating and the consequences on RRI variables (Rip, 2016).

In the case of DigiTeRRI's task 2.4, we have therefore integrated into the data collection tool questions related to the tasks (operational description of the activities of the actor under study), observable elements related to these tasks, and questions concerning the expected results in terms of RRI. For RRI evaluation it was not possible to use the self-assessment tool available on the RRI Tools website. Our interviewees wished to describe their practice by interview only and the time required for the self-assessment was not compatible with the time allowed. Finally, we summarized the questions by major RRI themes.

3. DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

Tools developed by the University of Lorraine and co-validated during two meetings with the leaders of Work Package 2.2 were made available to the partners to facilitate the collection of data on digitization practices. More specifically, a guide to assist in the data collection was developed (see appendix). It contains a questionnaire and explanations. A video designed by the University of Lorraine and produced by WeDo served as a tutorial. Finally, an internet platform allowed the partners to download the collected data.

4. OUTCOMES

A total of 37 interviews were conducted by the consortium members and 36 practices were identified and described (table one and figure two):

Table 1. List of observed practices

NO	DESCRIPTION OF PRACTICE
1	72 Hours to develop Agile projects to foster Digital Innovation: It is a training module shared between students and company executives.
2	Institut des services et industries du Futur de Troyes is an institute that brings together academics, companies and public institutions in order to reflect and develop digitalisation solutions, prepare a future economy and train managers and citizens. Four mains tasks: education, research, discussion between stakeholders and demonstrators
3	Platform industry 4.0 private association: mutualization of equipment and human resources. For relevant stakeholder groups the aim is to help product and process design, to improve the conditions for implementation and to promote exchange: participative projects, technology-related collective studies, mutual learning between the members, human-centred approach of digitalization
4	Cooperation Network: research, science, open innovation, cooperation, technology and knowledge transfer, RRI, digitization in cooperation
5	Disabled testing group: an acceptability assessment group is composed of physical disabled people, people with mental or social problems. They give their reaction when trying to use new

NO	DESCRIPTION OF PRACTICE
	digital tools under study. The strategy: the same tools for everyone. Example: city information web site.
6	<p>AIP Primeca / S-Mart factory of the future platform: The goal is to develop a factory-school where students and employees of companies can acquire skills in the field of production of parts in a digitalized context. The platform allows the implementation of agile and reconfigurable production, and the use of recyclable materials. But it also allows to study the regeneration of old products. On this platform there are robots, cobots, automated machines, lean management tools, automated workshops and sensors. The concept of product supporting its own data is also developed in this platform.</p>
7	<p>New academic courses and new digital academic organization: transformation to digital learning (teaching, examination, communication with students) to develop skills in the field of the future factory</p>
8	<p>Regional master plan grassfire network to reach the European defined standard of 100 Mbit,</p>
9	<p>Lycée 4.0.: Since 2017, it is a plan to deploy digital educational action. It provides all secondary school students (public, private, professional, agricultural, technical), approximately 200,000 students - 353 secondary schools (from the second to the final year) with a digital tool (computer) to access educational resources (replacing textbooks, school books, in order to familiarise themselves as best as possible with the uses of digital technology, to benefit from modern working conditions, responding to today's educational challenges and helping to facilitate their professional integration. Access to 3000 digital educational resources. 8,000 references, including 3,500 manuals via the ENT Digital Workspace access " My Digital Office ". The ENT represents the strategic tool and the unique communication channel of the Region for families and pupils. The student becomes the owner of the computer at the end of his/her schooling. Only region in France to apply this approach for the target in question</p>
10	<p>Serious Games. The idea of creating the Serious Games comes after the political will to deploy a "Factory of the Future" plan from 2016 at national and regional level. The CCI (Chamber of Industry and Commerce) is fully committed to this plan. As part of the regional "Factory of the Future" plan, supported by the Region for business development, the Alsace CCI launched a major survey at the end of 2015 to identify companies with cutting-edge know-how and technologies that are able to transform a company into the industry of the future. 170 solution providers were identified, with cutting-edge expertise in 10 areas: productivity; agility; human</p>

NO	DESCRIPTION OF PRACTICE
	<p>factor; deadlines; digital; customer relations; business model; energy; design; modelling. This game was thought up during a working group led by the CCI with the regional companies offering technological solutions (community) with the aim of making themselves better known and also to make them aware of the stakes of their technologies for companies. This game is a technological showcase of the industry of the future accessible to all people (company, student, public player, citizen ...), no age is required to become familiar with the technologies. It allows starting from a problem (human, organizational, product, management, strategy ...), based on real business situations, to find an associated technology, according to a business project or the development of a theme. The local solution providers are referenced in a directory by technological brick and therefore the company has the possibility to identify providers solutions after the game to move forward on its project. www.offreursdesolutions.fr It's a private initiative built by partner companies, supported and labelled by AIF (Alliance Industrie du Futur at the national level). The platform is hosted by the CCI (no risk of product stoppage)</p>
11	<p>Simplon school. Short Description : Project DNA - Digital training school based on an inclusion model serving people who are far from employment, people with disabilities, refugees, women, young people without diplomas, newcomers, etc.) and the most disadvantaged territories while promoting as much as possible gender, age and social and geographical diversity: "make digital technology a real inclusionary lever to reveal different talents that are not well represented in digital technology and digital technical professions (basic, CNF, etc.)". Simplon.co's positions concern the code for all, gender parity in the digital world and the Social and Solidarity Economy, the battle for youth employment, the revitalisation of territories including working-class districts, rural areas and overseas territories. 82 Factories ("social franchises") - training centres including 20 abroad (15 countries) no presence in Sweden or Austria to date - located in rural territories, overseas and not only in working-class districts and large conurbations. Distinction: genuinely open to all (regardless of age, no diploma requirements) and entirely free of charge for learners, it is also one of the key players who, since its inception, has been integrating a central concern regarding the representation of women in these professions which are not very feminised. Value, impact of the project: Over the last two years, driven by the maintenance of a very high level of skill needs in the digital field, Simplon.co has multiplied its social impact by four and trained more than 5,600 people worldwide in digital professions with a positive exit rate of 75% (6 months after training). International development is ongoing.</p>

NO	DESCRIPTION OF PRACTICE
12	Online platform for companies in Bruck an der Mur: Homepage for companies which have little or no digital media or no online platform which is financed by the initiative.
13	workshop in Styria - workshops throughout Austria with companies: Identify IT competencies of employees for companies and develop through workshops which competencies are important, e.g. accounting software, IT security etc.
14	Digital Material Valley Styria: to support industrial companies through projects to carry out the digital transformation
15	Project "Voladigital" from the University of Technology Graz: Understanding and using the competence requirements of digitisation. Development of a training platform and to create a training concept for SMEs for digital practices
16	Regional political involvement: Role of a regional manager, responsible for the implementation of the strategy concept that applies throughout Styria at regional level (Bruck-Mürzzuschlag). Digital skills
17	The Wood Region: a cluster dedicated to the development of additive manufacturing
18	Industrie 4.0 (national funding programme) Short description: non-repayable grant for enabling digital change in the production sector integrating the costs of: analysis, investments, consulting and training for employees
19	Toolbox (a tool for family businesses): In response to the question of how family businesses can shape their future responsibly, CAMPUS 02 has developed an overall model with which this particular type of business can be optimally prepared, accompanied and supported for digital change. This model takes into account all components of the overall situation, leaves the responsible decision-makers at the centre of the digital transformation project and uses the instruments developed specifically for family businesses to ensure sustainable business development. Thanks to these developments at CAMPUS 02, entrepreneurial families and owners can now find answers to many questions more easily, in a practice-oriented manner and with the aim of being successful in a digital world. The model has already been tested in practice and can be successfully applied in the future to accompany digital transformation processes of family businesses.
20	HiWay - a new SME working as a provider of data lines

NO	DESCRIPTION OF PRACTICE
21	Fit4internet: a program aiming at an increase of digital competence in Styria
22	Higher Technical Education (Engineer) on Information Technology (IT) and SMART Production, Education in secondary school segment
23	Science education, new study programs bachelor study on "Industrial Data Science" and integration of digitalization courses in already existing study program of mining and tunneling (specialization on digitalization), Sensor technologies, computational networks, cloud computing, big data analysis, artificial intelligence applications in engineering, computational learning, computational simulation, new technologies in automatization
24	Pilot action for more higher qualification and research resource of young people, science education (RRI), PHD initiative, new pool of PHD positions, approx. 30 positions, knowledge cluster in the territory, become a hot spot in science education and research, more initiative, more projects, infrastructure pilot action for academic knowledge work market in digitalization initiative
25	Robotlyftet - An organization with the goal to support the Industrial SMEs of the Värmland region through different initiatives in their robotization process
26	Be Digital: a program of the Compare structure to assist companies
27	Rythmes et Sons company - Digitalisation of the production process. This practice explains how a traditional SME (production of flight cases) digitalised its process of production through the introduction of digital tools, integration of a young engineer (training period, short time contract, full time job) and cooperation between a laboratory and the company for the transfer knowledge. The project was funded by Region Alsace (Region Grand Est) using the program Hommes resources (50% of the gross salary of the hired people funded through a grant for a period of 6 to 18 months). The setting up and the follow up of the project were delegated by the Regional Authority to the Regional Innovation Agency, Grand E-nov.
28	ACES: research and coordination program in the field of additive manufacturing
29	The Regional Executive Board and Regional Council have formed a long-term development digitalization strategy that defines both the what's and how's. Focus on both innovative new practices, cost-efficiency and value for the people of Värmland. In terms of regional development, we have a regional development strategy and a smart specialization strategy. Within in S3 we have pointed out digitalization as one of the main drivers for change.

NO	DESCRIPTION OF PRACTICE
30	Implementation of an open-collaboration platform for the manufacturing- and innovation-ecosystem
31	Digitalwell Arena: program aiming the development of digitalization in the field of wealth
32	Fabrique Collective de la Culture du Libre: this is an initiative aiming the development of the use of freeware. A specific space with equipment welcome people to teach them how to use freeware, in different domains: office automation, data search, and also working functionalities as accounting
33	Artificial Intelligence Plan (Grand Est). The President of the Grand Est Region, Jean Rottner, presented the Artificial Intelligence regional plan at “360 Possibles event” (27th of June 2019). This plan has 5 objectives for 5 years: to boost business competitiveness, support scientific excellence, support the development of start-ups, develop regional skills on the topic, ensure transparent, ethical and inclusive AI. The last point is directly linked to DIGITeRRI project. This plan is part - and this is its great strength - in a real European dynamic, and the link with Germany (Three landers : Baden-Wurtemberg, Saarland, Rheinland-Pfalz), Belgium (Wallonia), Luxembourg and Switzerland (from Basel to Zurich) to federate businesses and academics within a real valley of the European artificial intelligence.
34	Axon fab lab: private company Fab Lab to foster design of innovative products and employees training
35	Digital fabrication (FabLab): a “third place” dedicated to the digital applications open to the public
36	Innovation management structure proposes funding and assistance for project leaders in the field of digitalization and assesses innovation capacity of the territory.

Figure 2: Number of practices described per country.

The interviews were very disrupted by the Covid 19 pandemic, the interlocutors could hardly be met and even contacted. We have, therefore, extended the duration of this collection phase in order to take this obstacle into account. Thus, we were able to meet our objectives in terms of the number of interviews and diversity of practices.

5. DATA TREATMENT: DESCRIPTION OF THE TERRITORIAL ECOSYSTEMS FOR DIGITALIZATION

5.1. Who is involved?

The practices supporting digitalization are carried out by a wide variety of actors:

- 9 are academic structures. They provide human resources either teachers or researchers. Some have recruited project managers. This is accompanied by investments in computer equipment. In some cases, these are organized into technical platforms,
- 10 of the public institutions. They provide guidance, communication, funding and participate to strategy.
- 2 of the production companies. They applied digitalization and transfer their experience to other companies and suppliers.
- 3 service companies: They provide guidance.
- 12 are private associative (cluster organization) or charitable structures. They help a large range of users.

We can therefore observe that public and private actors intervene either directly or by creating specific structures to carry out digitalization support practices.

5.2. Who are the beneficiaries?

Figure 3 gives the outcomes of the census of the people targeted by the practices per type of stakeholders.

Figure 3: Beneficiaries per practice and per targeted domain.

Figure 3 gives the number of times a particular beneficiary is cited for one particular practice and domain. We can observe that the stakeholders propose practices that address a wide spectrum of users. Only 7 structures can be considered as more specialized with a maximum of 5 target categories. The consultancy structures and researchers are targeted by stakeholders that try to assist them in the field of technology exclusively. Companies and entrepreneurs are the recipients of stakeholders that try to assist them both in the domains of technology and but also work (organizational aspects) and employment. No surprising, public institutions and associations are targeted when the digitalization process has a general territorial impact. Note that citizens constitute major concern in different domains: general education, technology, and professional abilities.

Moreover, data analysis shows that:

- Academic structures have a wide range of beneficiaries. Only citizens sometimes do not have access to certain services. There is a very strong opening towards industrial clients.

- Public institutions can be divided into two categories: those that are open to all or those that are highly specialized.
- Production companies rarely target students (except for internships). They are mainly active in the world of work but may have a broader scope if they are mutualized structures.
- The "other" structures are very diverse (including clusters), even if they rarely target students.

We therefore have here a first element of conclusion concerning the ecosystem oriented towards digitization. Whatever the territory, there is a phenomenon of "overlapping", all categories of the population can have access to multiple interlocutors. The context is therefore rich, entrepreneurial, and very little categorized.

5.3 An ecosystem with many interactions

The functioning of the actors is based on partnership. Only one practice is carried out by a structure totally in-house. 163 partners are thus involved in the 36 practices.

We note that:

- Academic structures work with institutions and companies in addition to collaborations with other universities. They are very much in demand as partners but 11 out of 36 actors do not collaborate with universities.
- All public institutions work together with other public institutions in the field of digitalization.
- Companies do not collaborate directly with social associations.

The form of the partnership has been also studied:

- The academic structures work with a contractual way and pecuniary contracts most of the time.
- Public institutions work essentially in non-pecuniary relation.
- All other actors work with a contractual and pecuniary context.

Figure 4: Types of contracts between stakeholders.

Overall, and even as a reminder, we have not tried to have a statistically representative approach (the distribution of the types of actors within the ecosystems of the three territories not being known at the outset), we note that 116 partnerships are the subject of a formal contract against 47 with an informal agreement. The **Figure 5** shows that: pecuniary relations are mainly formal, and half of the non-pecuniary relationships are formal.

This corresponds to several situations, essentially, the partners are working within the framework of a project paid for by the project's pilot. Sometimes it is a subcontracting relationship.

Figure 5: Form and pecuniary dimension of the partnerships (DP-n refers to the Digital Practice number n).

5.4 The targeted impact of the practices on the digitalization maturity of the beneficiaries

The Digital Maturity Model helps identify the progression expected from the beneficiaries of the practice. The following figures shows for each practice:

- The nature of the objectives (Figure 5): strategy, individual leadership, technical evolution of the products, the internal organization of the organizations (operations), the culture of digitalization, the skills of the individuals, the governance of the structures, the production technology,
- The starting levels (Figure 6). It is the diagnosis of each practitioner about the current situation.

- As a remind, the increasing levels of maturity are: unaware (in dark red colour on the figure) / conceptual (in red colour on the figure) / defined (in orange colour on the figure) / integrated (in green colour on the figure) / transformed (in dark green colour on the figure).

The **Figure 6** the targeted Digital Maturity Diagram helps understand the stakeholder's ambitions, while, Figure 6, about the current Digital Maturity Diagram indicates the vision of the stakeholders about the present situation on their territory. The greener boxes we have, the greater the ambition, on the other hand, the redder boxes we have, the less the dimension is taken into account.

Figure 6: Expected Digital Maturity Level for each practice and each dimension.

The following elements can be concluded, following the x-axis in **Figure 6**:

- In terms of strategic thinking: 29 practices out of 36 aim at a perfect expertise of the beneficiaries ("transformed" or "integrated"). The aim is to help them understand and define the future profile of their digitized activities. Beneficiaries must acquire a very clear vision of what their business should become (individuals), their operations and products (companies and associations) and the requirements of online services (citizens). 7 practices are not at all interested in this dimension.
- 26 practices aimed at improving the mastery of digitization by organization leaders. The current situation (figure 6) starts from a low to medium initial situation (21 initial situations deemed "unaware, "conceptual or defined"). In addition, 15 initial situations are judged "integrated" or "transformed". It can be hypothesized that two categories of leaders must be distinguished. Those who generally understand that digitalization will have an impact on management and go before boards, while others have difficulty in defining the nature of these changes and must be proactively sensitized by the ecosystem. We note that the practices are aimed at taking leaders to "one upper level". This may seem modest. 5 practices are not interested in this dimension.
- The ambition concerning the technical transformation of products is great: 18 practices seek to ensure that the beneficiaries are fully capable of modifying their products and services. However, the initial situation is quite low, since only two initial "integrated" levels are identified. So many practices integrate a "hard" and technological dimension of digitalization.
- 20 practices aim at the maximum level concerning the control of internal processes (operations) of organizations. The starting level is disparate, with 10 initial levels considered "conceptual" and 15 with an "integrated" or "transformed" level. So, there are two kinds of practices in this field: upgrading and specialization.
- 16 practices show the maximum targeted level in the cultural dimension. The others are less ambitious. 12 practices start from the observation of strong initial weakness on the part of the targets (12 practices less than or equal to "conceptual"). This confirms situations known as the "digital divide".
- The "people" section relates to individual skills. The actors consider that the initial situation is very varied, they face audiences with very strong differences in terms of digital skills. On the other hand, the ambition of the stakeholders is very high for everyone,
- Governance seems to be a more difficult subject for ecosystem actors to deal with. The aim of practices is almost systematically to move the beneficiaries from one level to another.
- Technology is the subject of special and priority treatment. Only a few rare practices do not seek to make their beneficiaries' technology evolve very strongly. Despite a very disparate initial situation, the ambition is maximum. The technique that covers here the way objects, services and cultural works are produced for companies, craftsmen and public service associations is at the heart of the concerns.

We note that overall the practices are very strongly aimed at providing support in the technical dimensions of digitization: digitization of products and services, support for the digitization of the organization (supply chain management, control of operations, evaluation among others) and production techniques (material or services). It is in these areas that the target levels are the highest.

It can be considered that the majority of practices integrate the culture and skills related to digitalization. However, the objective of raising awareness among individuals and transmitting a new culture to them is approached more cautiously by the actors.

Figure 7: Current Digital Maturity Diagram for each of the practices and each dimension.

On **Figure 7** the greener boxes we have, the more favourable the initial situation is, conversely, the more red boxes we have, the lower the initial level is.

Globally, stakeholders point out obstacles in every domain. But this diagram confirms that the diagnosis about people capacity is controversial: the gap between highly competent and non-aware people seems to exist on each territory. Moreover, stakeholders consider that the current level about internal operations (organization) of companies and other structures is the most critical variable. Practices that address management (leadership and governance) pose problems for ecosystems because the targeted progression is low (only one level of maturity). Two hypotheses exist: the beneficiaries are not applicants for training and/or advice, or the actors are not very capable of addressing these aspects. This poses a problem because digitalization changes professional situations and therefore the hierarchical links and overall management of women and men in the structures.

Finally, the skills of developing visions for individuals and strategic policies for organizations can be seen as a practice led by specialists.

5.5 The main claimed obstacles

The obstacles that territorial stakeholders say they encounter give an idea of their intervention framework but also of the meaning they give to their actions.

The classic theme mentioned during the interviews is access to budgets because support for digitization requires hours of work to be financed but also equipment. There are also remarks concerning equipment (internet access, cost of certain tools such as office automation, telephone costs, etc.).

We also note other constraints:

- The positioning of training courses in digitalization organized by the ecosystem is sometimes difficult compared to existing training courses. It is not easy to find free time in existing courses. Moreover, the recognition of a "digitalization" specialty is not always simple because the corresponding skills are transversal (one can train people with a profile of mechanics, financiers, social workers, etc.),
- Citizen acceptability is also sometimes limiting. Digitalization is a process of change that provokes positive or negative reactions like any change,
- Administrative obstacles are also mentioned. In particular, the timing of obtaining public budgets and spending deadlines are sometimes problematic,

- Problems between local entities or between levels of decision-making (city/territory/state) exist. Some national entities in charge of digitization do not always support local initiatives. This is for example the case for national initiatives to promote the "industry of the future" and territorial initiatives on digitization,
- Work about digitalization is sometimes complex with some companies. The following obstacles can be observed: some entities have their headquarters outside the territory, which hinders the collaboration of these companies with local ecosystems, some small companies are reluctant to join mutualized platforms,
- Continuity of support is also a problem. For example, citizens or students may encounter computer issues at any time, so it should be necessary to offer assistance 24 hours a day.

Thus, beyond the classic problems of project management, the ecosystem encounters problems that attest to the following:

- The ecosystem wishes to work with any type of company.
- Recognition of skills acquisition by the beneficiaries of ecosystem actions is desired.
- It is necessary to make a long accompaniment. This poses a problem of continuity of practices but also problems of a purely technical nature. The computer equipment is subject to failure.
- The cultural paradox is often present. The ecosystem gives it a medium importance (see above) yet the reluctance to do to the ecosystem is often cultural.

6. DIGITALIZATION AND RRI IN TERRITORIES

The assessment of the adequacy of the conduct of the practices with the RRI principles was made during the interviews. Noting that the interviewees were not *a priori* aware of the dimensions of the RRI. They were answering questions without having received any information about the framework. The following figure gives the number of practices having a link with a particular RRI item. It indicates the sense of each action.

Figure 8: RRI evaluation of each digital practice.

The results for each dimension of the RRI are as follows:

- Gender balance in the team managing the practice: 22 practices out of 36 are piloted by teams made up of as many women as men. Several projects are led by women. In many cases, the piloting reflects the structure's gender ratio. Some actors regret the lack of female experts, while others note that they deal with few male candidates. Some actors claim to be "neutral" and consider that gender is not a criterion to be considered.

- 23 practices state that they aim to achieve a gender balance for their beneficiaries. Many actors are perfectly neutral on this point: the services offered are the same regardless of gender and the same applies to the conditions of access. Some speak of a desire to have a balanced audience but do not translate this into a quantitative objective,
- 23 practices display the objective of a future gender balance in terms of acquired skills, in a certain area of society or in a professional field. 2 practices are programs reserved for women.
- 10 practices report the confidentiality of the data used and produced during the practice. These situations systematically concern an industrial actor or beneficiary. However, in detail, data management is very diverse for the 26 other practices. Some actors in the ecosystem keep personal data on beneficiaries confidential but disseminate global and anonymous results of their action. Other operators disseminate global data but reserve concrete results for each beneficiary.
- 29 practices are widely communicated and disseminated. For the 7 others, the communication is reserved to the group of direct beneficiaries. The media are diverse with a predominance of the web,
- 11 actors do not use social networks as a resource for the functioning of the practice. For the other practices, there are remote workshops, the use of forums, surveys by email, see Facebook or LinkedIn.
- The question of the conflict of interest is treated very differently within the panel (20 "no" and 16 "yes"). Some stakeholders assume that their attention is only directed toward their beneficiaries so that the value generated by the practice is only for the latter. Others consider that this topic does not exist in their case (some academic for example). Finally, some public institution states that conflict of interest is a major concern they treat upstream the practice,
- All practices but one (within a company having already strong human resources procedures) integrate a procedure in order to avoid the dissemination of personal data,
- 24 practices start with a risk vs value analysis. Most of the practices that involved private stakeholders integrate this kind of analysis with a special focus on financial risk vs potential margins. Some stakeholders have a regular external evaluation of their activity. Many stakeholders claim that their practices are obviously positive and that a rigorous evaluation is not necessary,
- 8 practices are not concerned by a homogenous distribution of the Value created thanks to the practice. Value is: competencies, finance, notoriety, well-being among others. Note that some practices are more dedicated to social categories and thus homogenous value distribution is not considered,
- 31 practices are organized in such a way that valorise each contributor,
- Ensuring a non-corporatist approach is an aspect addressed for 26 practices. In the other cases, stakeholders address beneficiaries individually and therefore cannot fully guarantee that they do not form

a corporation. In addition, some corporations may be known to be the financiers of the practice. Finally, for 4 practices, this question is not deemed adequate,

- Composite governance: this issue was treated differently depending on the actors. All consider that they have composite governance from a cultural point of view. But academic structures, for example, are run by academics and therefore some actors see this situation as a limit to the diversity of governance. So, this question of diversity is very present, but the answers "yes" or "no" remain very subjective,
- Only 4 practices were organized without involving users. Many actors report prior needs analysis through interviews, design workshops with users and pilot tests.
- As seen above, 25 practices call upon academic structures at a certain stage. Thus, contact with these resource centres are widespread,
- 17 practices are conducted without contact with political representatives. This is sometimes done by academic structures or companies. There are 27 practices mobilizing public institutions. However, among the 9 others, the actors refer to simple initial consultations which are not considered as a real involvement.
- 18 practices include scientific training. This is to be put in relation with the strong orientation seen previously towards assistance in the transformation of products, operations and technology. These scientific training is generally provided by academics but not only,
- In connection with the above answer, 17 practices could be promoted by scientific journals.

To conclude, most of the practices are in line with the RRI's ethical principles. Even if this acronym and its meaning is not known, there is a real willingness among stakeholders to be in line with the RRI:

- For gender equality, this is only considered an objective for a few specific practices targeting women. For the other actors, their action is not dedicated to this but must be able to facilitate gender equality as an induced effect. So, gender equality is well embedded in their initiatives. This conclusion is consistent with some RRI-Practice project statements¹. Note that two aspects must be distinguished in the case of academic structures: gender equality may be formalized in the management of projects (parity between men and women in the composition of juries of project evaluation among others) but is not written as an objective in the project's objectives.
- Depending on the type of beneficiaries, two options appear for the "non-corporate" and "value diffusion" dimensions of the RRI. For practices with a broad spectrum of beneficiaries, these two aspects are taken into account, less so for those targeting specific social groups,

¹ <https://www.rri-practice.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/RRI-Practice-Policy-Briefs-Deliverable-17.4.pdf>

- All practices integrate a communication that is meant to be important and digitized (web). In half of the cases, this communication passes partly through scientific channels,
- Elements already analysed previously are verified: the actors largely call upon nearby public institutions and academics to design and implement their practice. There is a real concern for openness,
- The consultation of elected politicians is not a rare phenomenon,
- Actors seek to place themselves in a context of efficiency by generating Value in a significant way and being aware of the few risks involved,
- Finally, the protection of personal data is generalized.

7. DESCRIPTION OF THE MAIN PRACTICES FOR DIGITALIZATION

We made groupings between practices considering similarities in terms of tasks, beneficiaries and expected results. We therefore describe here generic "good practices" by highlighting territorial originality.

7.1 Training

Interesting practices have been set up in the territories to enable the acquisition of digital skills. There is a series of innovations in teaching methods that are undoubtedly adapted to the field of digitalization.

- ❖ Inclusive new courses Practice: *Simplon school* is based in Grand Est. It is a digital training school based on a social inclusion model serving people who are far from employment, people with disabilities, refugees, women, young people without diplomas, newcomers, etc.) within the most disadvantaged territories while promoting as much as possible gender, age and social and geographical diversity. The aim is to make digital technology a real inclusionary lever to reveal different talents that are not well represented in digital technology and digital technical professions (basic, CNF, etc.). *Simplon.co's* integrates a central concern regarding the representation of women in these professions which are not very feminized. Value, impact of the project. A complementary practice is organized in Styria by the *Regional management of zam Steiermark GmbH*, it focuses on job seekers and succeed in developing high-quality teaching but taking an initial very low threshold access.

- ❖ Pratique « 72 heures agiles » (Grand Est): This training module is intended for students and company executives. One of the originalities is to train the two types of populations together over a short period of time and to have them work on a company problem directly. This leads to a joint acquisition of skills, exchanges on the challenges of digitalization and the emergence of solution concepts for the company. This practice requires significant marketing work,
- ❖ New curriculum creation practice. At different levels new courses are launched about information technology, smart production, sensor technologies, computational networks, cloud computing, big data analysis, artificial intelligence, applications in engineering, computational learning, computational simulation, new technologies in automatization. This is the case at *Höhere Technische Lehranstalt Leoben* (Styria) at engineer level and also at *Montanuniversitaet* at Bachelor degree. Educational structures create new courses and sometimes new diplomas. This required finding local expertise.
- ❖ E-learning practices: the transition to e-learning focuses on training, evaluation and communication. The *Loeben Montanuniversitaet* (Styria) has set up an e-learning task force to steer this development. The practice integrates training courses, webinars, information... It allows, beyond the training, to communicate externally on topics related to digitalization. This approach can also be aimed at external users: in Styria, for example, the University of Graz has set up the *Voladigital* project, which provides access to tutorials for employees of SMEs.
- ❖ Serious Game Practice : In Grand Est, as part of the regional "Factory of the Future" plan, supported by the Region for business development, the Alsace CCI launched a major survey at the end of 2015 to identify companies with cutting-edge know-how and technologies that are able to transform a company into the industry of the future. 170 solution providers were identified, with cutting-edge expertise in 10 areas: productivity; agility; human factor; deadlines; digital; customer relations; business model; energy; design; modelling. *Offreurdresolution.fr game* was thought up collectively with the aim of making solution providers better known and to make them aware of the stakes of their technologies for companies. This game is a technological showcase of the industry of the future accessible to all people (company, student, public player, citizen ...), no age is required to become familiar with the technologies. It allows starting from a problem (human, organizational, product, management, strategy ...), based on real business situations, to find an associated technology, according to a business project or the development of a theme. The local solution providers are referenced in a directory by technological brick and therefore the company has the possibility to identify providers solutions after the game to move forward on its project. The platform is hosted by the CCI (no risk of product stoppage),

- ❖ Family business support practice. The University of Graz has developed a specific *toolbox for family-owned businesses*. CAMPUS 02 has developed an overall model with which this particular type of business can be optimally prepared, accompanied and supported for digital change. This model takes into account all components of the overall situation, leaves the responsible decision makers at the centre of the digital transformation project and uses the instruments developed specifically for family businesses to ensure sustainable business development. Thanks to these developments, entrepreneurial families and owners can now find answers to many questions more easily, in a practice-oriented manner and with the aim of being successful in a digital world.
- ❖ Collective workshop practice: all over Styria workshop are organized focusing on digitalization. The aim is both to help companies' employees to acquire competencies and to get a better understanding on the specific problems of companies. These *inter-company workshop* help in the use of new tools or to stimulate different use of present tools.

7.2 Technical Platforms

- ❖ Practical "industry of the future" platform. There is a development of technical platforms dedicated to the support of companies. They enable the pooling of equipment, provide training and carry out technical studies. Among the main equipment are automated production lines, robots, cobots, sensors and process control stations. The Österreich Industry 4.0 Platform is a private association of Styria that contracts with its members and customers. It is also involved in standardization and acts as a partner for international programs. We note that because of its experience its area of intervention goes beyond the territory. In Grand Est, the platform *AIP PRIMECA / S-MART* aims to develop a factory/school where students and industrial employees improve their skills in the field of parts' production in a context of digitalization. The platform allows agile, reconfigurable production and the use of recycled raw material. But also, focuses on the regeneration of "old" product. The concept of products storing their own data is developed. A connexion with the cloud to enrich the internal database with open data is also in place.
- ❖ Fab Labs are developing in the territories. They are university platforms open to companies, citizens, students and sometimes citizens. Associations practicing open access are being set up in cities and rural areas. Finally, companies (Axon cable for example) are integrating a Fab Lab to complete the tools available to designers. In the case of this company, the Fab Lab is also open to any employee for personal projects and training.

7.3 Clustering

- ❖ Multi-stakeholder clustering practice: this involves creating spaces for dialogue, project development, lobbying, setting up shared technical support and advice. This for multiple actors. The challenge is to gather all the necessary skills around the theme of digitalization, and, to coordinate training, consulting and material investments. The goal is also to give visibility to the support process. In Grand Est, the University of Troyes has taken the initiative of this type of cluster in its employment area. Called "*Institut des services et industries du Futur de Troyes*", one of the originalities is to build technical solutions through research.
- ❖ Open innovation platform: in Grand Est, Matériaia which is a cluster dedicated to the material transformation sector launches an *open-collaboration platform for the manufacturing- and innovation-ecosystem*. It aims to stimulate open innovation between any kind of stakeholders. Like the platform of big innovative companies, this tool tries to create a dynamic of creativity, information exchange, and collaboration in the territory.
- ❖ Participatory Research Practice: Faced with the complexity of societal issues, the University of Graz (Styria) has set up a participatory research practice. This is an open model where focus groups are set up to develop research topics and guide scientific policy. The Connecting *Ideas4research* approach has been implemented in various fields: medicine, culture and architecture. Ethical issues are addressed.
- ❖ Shared consulting practice: industrial clusters are organizing themselves to have a consulting structure. In Styria, the *Digital Material Valley Styria*, supports companies in problem solving. The advice is technical and mainly focused on production: image processing, robotics, smart product. The consulting is fee-based. Also, in Värmland, the "*wood region*" cluster assists companies, particularly in the areas of design and additive manufacturing. Always in Värmland, *IUC / Stål & Verkstad*, also plays this role by adding a sustainability dimension. Finally, in this territory, the structure called *Compare* highlights its ability to innovate, i.e. to create digital products for its members (including the health sector). Some mutualized structures are specialized in a particular field of digitalization, such as the *Alfred Nobel Science Park* in Värmland, which focuses on additive manufacturing.
- ❖ Holistic practice: more generally, devices are created to take into account the whole sequence from start to digitization: call for consultants to frame projects, training, study of solutions and investment. These measures provide financial assistance and create repayment conditions that strongly limit the risks for the beneficiaries. A program of this type exists in Styria: *Industry 4.0 funding program*. In the Grand Est a

program called "*Ressource Homme*" allows a small business to hire a young person of high level (50% of the salary taken in charge for 12/18 months). The French company *Rythmes et Son* took advantage of this opportunity to go digital by recruiting a young engineer who is technically competent and skilled in project management and by forging links with the University.

- ❖ Specialized consulting practice: private consulting companies are developing to help those in charge of economic activities to make their choices in the offer of materials available on the market. Potential customers do not always have the in-house specialists to make choices to take into account other elements than the purchase price. These private structures assume the advice and sometimes also the supply of equipment. This is the case of the SME *HiWay* in Styria, which specializes in connectivity.

7.4 Integration of Users in service design

- ❖ Practice for the integration of people in difficulty: the practice of integrating users from the upstream stages of innovative projects has shown its value in terms of a better adaptation to the need, greater acceptability, helping to apprehend the future innovation according to different visions and to adopt a more agile approach. In Grand Est, the City of Nancy's digital development department is leading focus groups dedicated to people in difficulty in designing its online services. People with physical disabilities or experiencing social integration problems participate in the design work with the developers. The aim is not to make specific tools but, on the contrary, to ensure that the same services are accessible to all.

7.5 Pooling of services

- ❖ Web marketing assistance practice. The promotion and sale of products and services online represents an important market regardless of the size of the company. Initiatives are implemented to provide online sales assistance for structures that do not have the means to create, maintain and renew a marketing site. <https://wirtschaft-bruckmur.at/> is an initiative of a community of Styria that aims to promote service companies and businesses in its territory. The companies benefit from the tool but also from the engineering.

7.6 Promotion of free software

- ❖ Practice of promoting free software: In the Grand Est, the City of Vandoeuvre les Nancy has launched the “*Fabrique Collective de la Culture du Libre*” (Collective Factory of Free Culture). This practice aims to help the population and structures of all kinds to master free software, to limit the distribution of their personal data on large commercial sites and to be able to live "digitally" at a lower cost. Training is provided for citizens in media libraries, with associations and soon with companies and business creators. Technical advice is also available thanks to computer specialists.

7.7 Research

- ❖ The research structures give an inflection in their scientific program to integrate the challenges of digitalization. This can take the form of financial and material efforts aimed at doctoral candidates. Thus, the Montanuniversitaet in Styria has launched a *program for 30 PhD positions* in the field of knowledge. The *Institut des services et industries du Futur de Troyes* has also mobilized funds for research, whether technological or in other fields: management, cognition, among others.
- ❖ The territories have set up processes to orient research towards digitalization (elaboration of political priorities), stimulate work (funding) and evaluate the impact of these devices on the territory. This is the case in Värmland via the innovation management agency (*Vinnova*).

7.8 Strategic Plan

- ❖ Regional planning practice: Each of the three regions (Styria, Värmland and Great East) have established a strategic plan at the regional government level. These plans were developed in a participatory manner. Guidelines are defined as well as financial incentives. Some particularities can be found in these plans, such as the Grand Est, which emphasizes artificial intelligence. In each territory, this strategic program aims to provide framework conditions and co-finance initiatives.

7.9 Investment for optical fibre

- ❖ Improving broadband infrastructure practice. Internet access is fundamental, and the European Community has set standards in this area. In Styria, Värmland and Grand Est, a fibre development plan has been put in place.

7.10 Supply of computer equipment

- ❖ Access to educational tools practice: in Grand Est is organized *Lycée 4.0*. Since 2017, a plan to deploy digital educational action: it provides all secondary school students (public, private, professional, agricultural, technical), approximately 200,000 students - 353 secondary schools (from the second to the final year) with a digital tool (computer) to access educational resources (replacing textbooks, school books, in order to familiarize themselves as best as possible with the uses of digital technology, to benefit from modern working conditions, responding to today's educational challenges and helping to facilitate their professional integration. Access to 3000 digital educational resources. 8,000 references, including 3,500 manuals via the ENT Digital Workspace access " My Digital Office ". The ENT represents the strategic tool and the unique communication channel of the Region for families and pupils. The student becomes the owner of the computer at the end of his/her schooling.

8. CONCLUSION

DigiTeRRI Task 2.4 consists in an analysis of a panel of digital practices within the three territories: Värmland, Styria and Grand Est.

We studied 36 practices showing diversity and a great involvement of territorial ecosystems. We point out that many of these local initiatives are in line with RRI principles.

The question is basically: can we consider these practices as “best practices” for anticipation, reflexivity, responsiveness and inclusion?

The DigiTeRRI project does not integrate a comparison between these practices or with other digital practices. Moreover, it seems difficult to make such a comparison as our study points out the complexity of territorial ecosystems and the former qualitative descriptive studies (task 2.2 and 2.3) highlight the very different local contexts.

However, as interviews reveal that some of these practices tend to become permanent, it appears that our practices panel is composed with “good practices”. This census will be useful to:

- Enter as input in the “vision definition” workshops,
- Be integrated in the possible deployment programs in the other territories.

In the further steps of DigiTeRRI, the 36 practices we have studied here and the propositions of stakeholders (visioning workshops) could be confronted to the recommendations proposed by the RRI community and EU projects members. This required a strong protocol to consider the different RRI scales (DigiTeRRI focuses on the territorial quadruple helix ecosystem and not only on academic structures or political institutions) and the characteristics of the digital domain. But obviously some of the so-called “best practices” described in the Handbook for Organisations Aimed at Strengthening Responsible Research and Innovation could be used as references to analyse our 36 practices panel².

² <https://www.rri-practice.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/RRI-Practice-Handbook-for-Organisations.pdf>

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ANNEX

DigiTeRRI Task 2.4: data collection guidelines

Responsible Research and Innovation Approach for Transitioning the
Traditional Industry Regions into Digitalised Industry Territories

DigiTeRRI

<https://DigiTeRRI.eu/>

WP 2.4 GUIDELINES

*Data collection and processing for
transition practices identification*

Before starting your mission within Task 2.4, about collecting digitalization practices,
please read these instructions.

Your material

task 2.4 Platform

To collect data, please use the platform developed by ERPI Team:

<https://enquetes.univ-lorraine.fr/index.php/544554?lang=en>

Thus, you will find there all the questions required to describe the digitalization. This platform is also designed to treat all data from the three territories and finally refer to the EC.

Task 2.4 Vidéo

Developed by ERPI Team and WeDo this YouTube video provides explanation about the goals of your mission.

https://youtu.be/_OUrrTo_l3c

This 3 minutes' video is a tutorial tool that presents the main objectives of task 2.4 objectives in order to help partners in their appropriation of the approach. Some definitions are given: what is a practice, what is a digital maturity model among others. The list of data to be collected in each territory and for each practice is detailed. The main guidelines to use the digital platform developed to aggregate the interviews outcomes are presented as well as the methodologies used by Université de Lorraine to treat the collected data.

Task 2.4 Guidelines

The present document you are reading gives all details about the fulfillment of your mission.

Your mission and our common objectives

We need to describe the R&I ecosystem in each territory. To do this we need to:

- Describe the actors involved,
- Understand their objectives, the context,
- Describe their practices.

Data collection and analysis (task 2.4)

We therefore propose that each territory should list the actions in favor of digitization carried out by the actors of the ecosystem according to the following grid. A practice is an organized and formalized action with well-defined means that aims to support the digitization of well-defined beneficiaries with due respect to RRI principles. Each territory should fill in as many grids as possible using an internet platform. Then, within the framework of task 2.4, an analysis will be carried out in order to identify:

- The similarity of actions between territories,
- Practices specific to a territory,
- A classification of practices according to beneficiaries and expected results,
- The analysis of practices that value the RRI criteria,

In fine a list of transition practices will be established.

Data collection responsibilities

It is the responsibility of each of the members of the DigiTeRRI project to describe practices in favor of digitalization on its territory. The more practices you collect the best database we commonly developed. We ask at least 5 practices per partner.

Note that we experienced the platform and we estimate that one hour maximum is necessary to describe a practice using the platform.

Data protection

You may choose to provide us with your personal data for further contact and collaboration within the DigiTeRRI project or, if you prefer, to fill in the questionnaire anonymously.

Moreover we need the name of the organization you are describing but if this organization will stay anonymous, we will deal with it. Any person giving you information may remain anonymous, the name of your interlocutor is not required. Note that the name of the organization will never appear in further

transversal analysis of the data base. For more information about data protection please contact:
Marianne.Hoerlesberger@ait.ac.at

The grid: necessary descriptive data about practices

A brief presentation of the practice

Observed actor who carries out the practice on the territory

- Name. We need the name of the organization. Any person giving you information may remain anonymous. Note that the name of the organization will not appear in further transversal analysis of the data base.
- Category: academic, public institutions, production company, service company, community,
- influence/expertise: the area in which the actor can make decisions (NB: this aspect is important to us to understand the competency profile of the actor),
- permanent and general professional goals: The objectives that the actor wants to achieve in order to fulfill his or her professional role (NB: this aspect is important to us to catch the basic mission of the considered stakeholder),
- main resources/means available to the actor NB: this gives information about the size and the operating power of the actor),
- main constraints: elements over which the actor has no power (NB: important to understand local specificities in terms of official limitation, legal constraints and deontology),
- Driving force for action: the indicators that the actor wants to improve.

Others Actors directly involved in the practice:

- Names
- Categories
- Form of collaboration with the pilot of the practice: formal / informal, pecuniary / non-pecuniary,

Targets/beneficiaries :

- Categories are

Education:

- students,
- citizens (like any people looking for a personal training, citizen unable to use internet tools or a practice aiming an improvement of the global digitalization skills in the society...)

Work and employment:

- citizens,
- entrepreneurs,
- big companies
- SME

Territory development:

- citizens,
- collectivities,
- policy makers,
- associations,

Innovation/technology:

- students,
- big companies,
- SME,
- researchers,
- consultancy companies and technical centers

Goals / expected results within the strict framework of practice

- Digitization : the goal is to improve the technique of the beneficiaries
- Digitalization : the goal is to accompany projects
- Organization/strategy: the goal is to define the strategy or accompany the global digital transformation

- digital maturity level: present and targeted : identify the position on the figure at the start of the practice and then the position wished at the end.

Maturity levels

Dimension	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed	
1. Strategy	Strategic vision, transformation roadmap					
2. Leadership	Management methods, sponsorship, resources					
3. Products	Business model, innovation capabilities, digital value chain					
4. Operations	Channels & business practices, processes, agility					
5. Culture	Customer centricity, hierarchy vs. network, openness					
6. People	Roles, expertise, capabilities					
7. Governance	Communication & collaboration rules, KPIs, alignment					
8. Technology	Software tools, cloud architecture, ICT infrastructure, Industry 4.0					

Practice / Intervention process: describe 4 main activities of people involved in the practice

- Sub-Activity one (describe the sub-activity 50/100 WORDS+ give one or observable)
- Sub-Activity Two (describe the sub-activity 50/100 WORDS + give one or observable)
- Sub-Activity Three (describe the sub-activity 50/100 WORDS + give one or observable)
- Sub-Activity Four (describe the sub-activity 50/100 WORDS + give one or observables)

This is important to get a better understanding of what is really done locally, how the practice is operated.

Sense of action in terms of RRI (please give argument and one or more observables)

- Gender equity
 - Gender balance in the group piloting the practice: yes no : 20/50 words argument

- Gender balance within all the beneficiaries: yes no : 20/50 words argument
- The gender equity is part of the practice itself: yes no : 20/50 words argument
- Open access
 - The data and information produced are on open access: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Publications diffusion: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Practice mobilize social media and networks: yes no : 20/50 words argument
- Ethics:
 - Conflict of interest: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Privacy respect: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Balance between risk and value: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Value creation equitable distribution: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Respect of all contributors: yes no : 20/50 words argument
- Governance
 - Un-corporatist governance: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Composite governance: yes no : 20/50 words argument
- Public engagement through the practice
 - Users contribution: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Academic contribution: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Politic engagement: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - Public institutions engagement: yes no : 20/50 words argument
- Science education
 - The practice integrates scientific training: yes no : 20/50 words argument
 - The practice integrates scientific communication: yes no : 20/50 words argument

Your comments

- Main interest according to you (author of the sheet)
- The limits according to you
- Your advices / conditions to generalize in other territories the practice in the form of a "good transition practice".

An example:

Responsible Research and Innovation Approach for Transitioning the
Traditional Industry Regions into Digitalised Industry Territories

DigiTeRRI

Task 2.4 Platform

<https://enquetes.univ-lorraine.fr/index.php/544554?lang=en>

**An example of
the description of
a practice with
the platform**

Proposed by

Enter the title and a Short description of the practice
Then give informations about the stakeholder

DigiTeRRI practices

0% 100%

Observed actor who carries out the practice on the territory

• 0. What is the digital practice ?

Title: 72 hours of Agile and Digital practices
Short description: during 3 days students and employees of some companies learn Agile digital project management. They follow short teaching modules, and, collectively applied the proposed methodologies on problematics given by the companies. The teams develop in 72 hours innovative prototypes of Web or Mobile applications by promoting Agile practices, user experiences and their skills in digital innovation.

• 1. What is the name of the stakeholder ?

UNIVERSITY OF LORRAINE
 ENSGSI
 Ecole Nationale Supérieure de Génie des
 Systèmes et de l'innovation

• 2. What is the type of this stakeholder ?
 Choose one of the following answers

Academic
 Public institution
 Production company
 Service company
 Community
 Other:

• 3. What is the influence and the expertise of the stakeholder ?

higher education
 research
 company and institution advices in the
 field of innovation

? Please specify the area in which the stakeholder can take decisions

• 4. What are its permanent and general professional goals ?

to train engineer
 to design new methodologies to pilot
 innovative projects
 to diffuse innovation methodologies

? The objectives that the stakeholder wants to achieve in order to fulfil his or her professional role

• 5. What are the main resources/means available to the stakeholder ?

- Professors, lecturers, researchers,
 - The Lorraine Fab Living Lab,
 - Software in the field of innovation,
 project management, decision taking...

6. What are its main constraints ?

Budget support of public institutions

? Please, specify the elements over which the stakeholder has no power

7. What are its driving force for action ?

innovation capacity of companies
Digitalisation in companies especially SME
Innovation and digitalisation skills of employees

? Please, specify the indicators that the stakeholders wants to improve over its territory

Following data relates to the ecosystem

Others Actors directly involved in the practice

8. Who are the others stakeholders directly involved in the practice ?

Stakeholder 1	non partnership
Stakeholder 2	
Stakeholder 3	
Stakeholder 4	
Stakeholder 5	
Stakeholder 6	
Stakeholder 7	
Stakeholder 8	
Stakeholder 9	
Stakeholder 10	

? Please fill in only the number of your partners

9. Indicate the category of the each stakeholder you mentioned above

- Academic
- Public Institution
- Production company
- Service company
- Community

Category	
Stakeholder 1	no partnership
Stakeholder 2	
Stakeholder 3	
Stakeholder 4	
Stakeholder 5	
Stakeholder 6	

10. What is the form of the collaboration with these stakeholders ?

	Formal	Informal	Pecuniary	Non-pecuniary	No answer
Stakeholder 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 6	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 7	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 8	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 9	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Stakeholder 10	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

? Please indicate if your collaboration is formal/informal **AND** pecuniary/non pecuniary

Then data focus on beneficiaries

Targets/beneficiaries of the practice

11. Education
Check any that apply

- Students
- Citizens

12. Work and employment
Check any that apply

- Citizens
- Entrepreneurs
- Big companies
- SME

13. Territory development
Check any that apply

- Citizens
- Collectivities
- Policy makers
- Associations

14. Innovation and technologies
Check any that apply

- Students
- Big companies
- SME
- Researchers
- Consultancy companies and technical centers

Resume later Next ▶ Exit and clear survey

What are the digitalization maturity level of the beneficiaries and then the objectives followed by the stakeholders thanks this practice?

0% 100%

Goals / expected results within the strict framework of practice

For this part, remember the different definitions

- Digitization : the goal is to improve the technique of the beneficiaries
 - Digitalization : the goal is to accompany projects
- Organization/strategy: the goal is to define the strategy or accompany the global digital transformation

This figure presents the digital maturity level.

15. Please, can you evaluate your current digital maturity level for each dimension

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Strategy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Leadership	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Products	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Operations	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Culture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
People	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Gouvernance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16. Please, can you evaluate your expected digital maturity level for each dimension

	Unaware	Conceptual	Defined	Integrated	Transformed
Strategy	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Products	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Operations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Culture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People	<input checked="" type="radio"/>				
Operations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Culture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Governance	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Resume later Next ▶ Exit and clear survey

How works this practice, what really do the stakeholder

Practice / Intervention process

*** 17. Describe 4 main activities of people involved in the practice**

	Description	One or several observable phenomena
Sub-Activity 1	defined topics	list of digitalization problem
Sub-Activity 2	gather students and indust	number of groups
Sub-Activity 3	manage teaching sequenc	planning, on line courses, s
Sub-Activity 4	evaluate results	prototypes, skill evaluation

Resume later Next ▶ Exit and clear survey

RRI evaluation of the practice

Sense of action in terms of RRI
Please give argument and one or more observables

*** 18. Gender balance in the group piloting the practice**
Choose one of the following answers

Yes
 No

Please enter your comment here:
ENSGSI mobilize as many female and male for this practice

*** 19. Gender balance within all the beneficiaries**
Choose one of the following answers

Yes
 No

Please enter your comment here:
But depending on the ratio in the group of targeted students

*** 20. The gender equity is part of the practice itself**
Choose one of the following answers

Yes
 No

Please enter your comment here:
the teaching is the same for student/industrial employees whatever their gender is

*** 21. The data and information produced are on open access**
Choose one of the following answers

Yes
 No

Please enter your comment here:
as the Agile Methodologies are applied on industrial problematic of digitalisation, each company keep the propriety of the results

*** 22. Publications diffusion**
Choose one of the following answers

Yes
 No

Please enter your comment here:
ENSGSI methodologies about agile digitalization project management are diffuse thanks internet

*** 23. Practice mobilize social media and networks**
Choose one of the following answers

Yes
 No

Please enter your comment here:

<p>* 24. Conflict of interest Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 30px;"></div>
<p>* 25. Privacy respect Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here: No <u>personal</u> information ask to participants</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 30px;"></div>
<p>* 26. Balance between risk and value Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here: <u>it is a training program without risk</u></p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 30px;"></div>
<p>* 27. Value creation equitable distribution Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here: <u>important: Value is for individuals (students and employees) in term of skills and for companies (getting digital prototypes)</u></p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 30px;"></div>
<p>* 28. Respect of all contributors Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 30px;"></div>
<p>* 29. Un-corporatist governance Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here: <u>ENSGSI is the only manager of the practice</u></p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 30px;"></div>

<p>* 30. Composite governance Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here:</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>* 31. Users contribution Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here: <u>when designing the program, companies have been ask to give their remarks and validation. And at the end of each module "72Hours" participants give their feedback</u></p>
<p>* 32. Academic contribution Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here: <u>ENSGSI is an academic structure. And methodologies taught have been improved by ERPI Laboratory</u></p>
<p>* 33. Politic engagement Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here:</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>* 33. Politic engagement Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here:</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>* 34. Public institutions engagement Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here:</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>* 35. The practice integrates scientific training Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here: <u>training about innovation management and digitalization</u></p>
<p>* 36. The practice integrates scientific communication Choose one of the following answers</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No</p>	<p>Please enter your comment here:</p> <input type="text"/>

Resume later Next ▶ Exit and clear survey

Could this practice be a DIGITERRI priority

Comments

• 37. What is the main interest according to you ?

the fact that in parallel, students and employees improve their skills in managing a digitalization project + the realisation in the form of prototypes

• 38. What are the limits according to you ?

not more than 4 companies involved on each site and for each module

• 39. According to you, what are your advices / conditions to generalize the practice in the form of "good transition practice" ?

- create a networks of structures managing the 72h practice
- develop a collaborative platform to pilot the network
- train trainers,

Resume later Submit Exit and clear survey